

PHOTOREDUCTION OF URANYL NITRATE BY TARTARIC ACID

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Measurements of the optical rotation of mixtures of uranyl nitrate and tartaric acid show that a complex compound is formed in solution. The photoreduction of this complex has been studied in the visible and ultraviolet regions.

Ghosh and Mitter (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 353) found that complex formation takes place between uranyl salt and various organic acids like tartaric, lactic, mandelic, etc. It is well known that uranyl salts are photochemically reduced by these acids: U^6 (yellow) $\rightarrow$ U^4 (green or blue).

Complex Formation.

When uranyl nitrate, $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, is added to *d*- or *l*-tartaric acid, the rotatory power of tartaric acid is enhanced. Measurements of the rotation of tartaric acid-uranyl mixtures, keeping the concentration of tartaric acid constant, gave maximum rotations for mixtures of the composition H_2T 4-uranyl (where T=tartrate ion). Assuming that in these mixtures complex formation is complete *i.e.*, concentration of complex = conc. of H_2T , the dissociation constant of the complex

$$K = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{[H_2T\text{-complex}] \times [\text{uranyl complex}]} \quad \dots (i)$$

was calculated as follows:

The observed rotation for any mixture is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Observed rotation} &= (\text{molecular rotation of complex}) \times [\text{complex}] \\ &+ (\text{molecular rotation of free } H_2T) \times [\text{free } H_2T] \quad \dots (ii) \end{aligned}$$

For mixtures giving maximum rotations, conc. of complex = conc. of H_2T , and we have from equation (ii),

$$\text{Observed rotation} = (\text{mol. rotation})_{\text{complex}} \times [H_2T],$$

$$\text{i.e., } (\text{mol. rotation})_{\text{complex}} = \frac{\text{observed maximum rotation for mixture}}{[H_2T]} \quad (iii)$$

similarly for free tartaric acid we have

$$(\text{Mol. rotation})_{\text{free } H_2T} = \frac{\text{observed rotation for free } H_2T}{[H_2T]} \quad \dots (iv)$$

From the observed rotation of any mixture, the concentration of the complex can be calculated from equations (ii), (iii) and (iv) by knowing the rotation of free tartaric acid and the maximal rotation for a set of mixtures. The dissociation constant K can then be calculated by substitution in equation (i).

The changes in the rotation of the mixtures were followed with a Winkel-Zeiss triple-field polarimeter which gave readings correct to 0.01° . The chemicals used were Merck's samples; the tartaric acids were recrystallised before use. Conductivity water was used for preparing the solutions. The value of K was calculated by measuring the rotations of 3 sets of mixtures, and the results are given below.

TABLE I.

Length of solution = 2.5 cm. $\lambda = 5893\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 25° .

Conc. of $d\text{-H}_2\text{T}$.	Conc. of n anyl.	Observed rotation.	Conc. of complex.	K .
0.250M	1.000M	+0.28°	0.250M	
"	0.500	+0.24	0.187	9.5
"	0.250	+0.21	0.140	11.6
"	0.125	+0.17	0.078	9.6
"	0.071	+0.15	0.047	9.7
"	0.031	+0.12	—	—
"	0.016	+0.12	—	—
"	—	+0.12	—	—
0.125	0.500	+0.14	0.125	
"	0.250	+0.11	0.078	9.6
"	0.062	+0.08	0.031	10.6
"	0.016	+0.06	—	—
"	0.004	+0.06	—	—
"	—	+0.06	—	—
0.062	0.250	+0.07	0.062	
"	0.125	+0.05	0.031	10.6
"	0.050	+0.04	0.016	10.2
"	0.031	+0.03	—	—
"	0.008	+0.03	—	—
"	—	+0.03	—	—

Mean value = 10.2

The results show that fairly concordant values are obtained for the dissociation constant K . As the concentration of uranyl is decreased, the concentration of complex in the mixture decreases; the rotation of the mixture also decreases until in the limit it is equal to that of free tartaric acid. The sign of the rotation of the complex is the same as that of tartaric acid. *l*-Tartaric acid forms complexes whose rotations are equal in magnitude but opposite in sign to those of *d*-tartaric acid.

Photoreduction.

The complex formed by the addition of uranyl nitrate to tartaric acid is photochemically reduced in the visible as well as in the ultraviolet; tartaric acid is oxidised and the uranyl salt is reduced to the uranous state, the colour change being from yellow to green. This reaction has been studied in the ultraviolet, violet and blue regions.

The experimental arrangement for studying the photo-reaction was the same as that described in a previous paper (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 507). The reaction was followed by the estimation of the reduced uranium. A known volume of an excess of standard permanganate was added in sulphuric acid solution to convert all the reduced uranium to the uranyl state, and the excess of permanganate was titrated iodimetrically. The whole process was carried out in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide to prevent oxidation of the uranous salt by air. There is no dark reaction for the mixtures studied, and the photochemical reaction is zero-molecular with respect to uranyl (U^6). Table II gives the effect of varying the concentration of the reactants on the velocity of the photoreduction in the ultraviolet. dx/dt refers throughout to the number of g. mols. transformed per minute. Unless otherwise stated, *d*-tartaric acid has been used.

Reaction in the Ultraviolet.

TABLE II.

$\lambda = 3130\text{\AA}$ (Chance Bros.). $p_n = 0.9$ to 1.3 . Temp. = 28° .

$$(dx/dt)_{\text{calc.}} = 20.52 \times 10^{-8} \cdot I_{\text{abs.}} \times \frac{[H_2T]}{0.2 + [H_2T]} \quad (\text{for all wave-lengths}).$$

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	$dx/dt \times 10^4$	
			obs.	calc.
0.500M	0.500M	7270 ergs	10.65	10.65
0.333	0.333	6570	8.60	8.45
0.250	0.250	6230	7.10	7.10
0.167	0.167	5710	5.45	5.35
0.125	0.125	5190	4.10	4.10

TABLE II (contd.).

Conc. of H ₂ T.	Conc. of uranyl.	<i>I</i> _{abs.}	<i>dx/dt</i> × 10 ⁴ .	
			obs.	calc.
0.500M	0.500M	7270 ergs	10.65	10.65
0.250	"	"	7.50	7.15
0.125	"	"	5.10	5.00
0.063	"	"	3.05	3.05
0.500	0.250	6230	9.10	9.15
0.250	"	"	7.10	7.10
0.125	"	"	4.85	4.90
0.063	"	"	3.00	3.05
0.500	0.125	5190	7.65	7.60
0.250	"	"	5.80	5.80
0.125	"	"	4.10	4.10
0.063	"	"	2.50	2.55

The velocity of the reaction decreases with decrease in equimolar concentration. Decrease in the concentration of tartaric acid, keeping the concentration of uranyl constant, results in a decrease in the velocity. Table III shows that, for the same mixture, the velocity of the reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of the light absorbed.

TABLE III.

$$\lambda = 3130 \text{ \AA.} \quad p_{\text{H}_2} = 0.9 \text{ to } 1.1. \quad \text{Temp.} = 28^\circ.$$

Conc. of H ₂ T.	Conc. of uranyl.	<i>I</i> at λ_{H_2}	<i>dt/dx</i> × 10 ⁴ .
0.50M	0.50M	7270 ergs	10.65
"	"	4670	6.90
"	"	3290	4.85
0.25	0.25	6230	7.10
"	"	3980	4.50
"	"	2840	3.25

Reaction in the Violet.—Table IV gives the effect of varying the concentration of the reactants on the velocity of the reaction in the violet region. Table V gives the effect of varying I_{abs} .

TABLE IV.

$\lambda = 4060\text{\AA}$ (Zeiss monochromat). $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0.9$ to 1.2 . Temp. = 28° .

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	I_{abs} .	$dx/dt \times 10^4$.	
			obs.	calc.
0.500M	0.500M	7700 ergs.	11.30	11.30
0.333	0.333	7000	9.40	9.00
0.250	0.250	6570	7.50	7.50
0.167	0.167	5530	5.30	5.15
0.125	0.125	4500	3.50	3.55
0.500	0.500	7700	11.30	11.30
0.250	"	"	8.60	8.80
0.125	"	"	6.15	6.30
0.063	"	"	3.70	3.75
0.500	0.250	6570	9.55	9.65
0.250	"	"	7.50	7.50
0.125	"	"	5.10	5.20
0.063	"	"	3.20	3.20

TABLE V.

$\lambda = 4060\text{\AA}$. $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0.9$ to 1.1 . Temp. = 28° .

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl	I_{abs} .	$dx/dt \times 10^4$.
0.500M	0.500M	7700 ergs.	11.30
"	"	5620	8.00
"	"	3580	5.75
0.250	0.250	6570	7.50
"	"	4240	5.55

The general nature of the reaction in the violet is the same as that in the ultraviolet. For the same mixture, the velocity is proportional to I_{abs} .

Reaction in the Blue.—Tables VI and VII give the results obtained for the photoreduction in the blue region. They are of the same type as those obtained in the ultraviolet and violet regions. The velocity of the reaction is proportional to the intensity of the blue light absorbed.

TABLE VI.

$\lambda = 4360 \text{ \AA}$ (Zeiss monochromat). $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0.9$ to 1.2 . Temp. = 28° .

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	I_{abs} .	obs. $dx/dt \times 10^4$.	calc.
0.500M	0.500M	4500 ergs.	6.60	6.60
0.333	0.333	4150	5.50	5.30
0.250	0.250	3770	4.30	4.30
0.167	0.167	3370	3.00	3.10
0.125	0.125	2850	2.20	2.25
0.500	0.500	4500	6.60	6.60
0.250	"	"	5.00	5.10
0.125	"	"	3.50	3.55
0.063	"	"	2.20	2.20
0.500	0.250	3770	5.60	5.75
0.250	"	"	4.30	4.30
0.125	"	"	3.00	3.00
0.063	"	"	1.70	1.85

TABLE VII.

$\lambda = 4360 \text{ \AA}$. $p_{\text{H}_2} = 0.9$ to 1.1 . Temp. = 28° .

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	I_{abs} .	$dx/dt \times 10^4$.
0.50M	0.50M	4500 ergs	6.6
"	"	2850	4.1
0.25	0.25	3770	4.3
"	"	2390	2.7

Reaction with d-, l- and r-Acids.—Some experiments were also carried out with *l*- and racemic-tartaric acids as reductants. The results given in Table VIII below show that there is no difference in the velocity of the photoreduction with these reductants in all the wave-lengths studied.

TABLE VIII.

 $p_n = 0.9$ to 1.1. Temp. = 28°.

Wave-length.	Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	$I_{abs.}$ for all complexes.	$d-H_2T$.	$l-H_2T$.	$r-H_2T$.
3130Å	0.50M	0.50M	7270 ergs.	10.65	10.60	10.60
"	0.25	0.25	6230	7.10	7.10	7.15
4060	0.50	0.50	7700	11.30	11.30	11.25
"	0.25	0.25	6570	7.50	7.45	7.50
4360	0.50	0.50	4500	6.60	6.55	6.60
"	0.25	0.25	3770	4.30	4.35	4.30

Table IX gives the quantum efficiency of the photo-process in the ultraviolet, violet and blue regions.

TABLE IX.

 $p_n = 0.9$ to 1.2. Temp. = 28°.

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of uranyl.	Quantum efficiency (γ).		
		3130Å.	4060Å.	4360Å.
0.500M	0.500M	4.7	3.6	3.4
0.250	0.250	3.6	2.8	2.6
0.125	0.125	2.5	2.1	1.8

The value of γ decreases with increasing wave-length of the radiation, and for the same wave-length, it decreases with decreasing concentration of the complex.

Reaction in Circularly Polarised Light.—The influence of *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light on the velocity of the photoreduction in the visible and in the ultraviolet regions was studied. Circularly polarised light was obtained by the combination of a polaroid and a Fresnel's rhomb for the visible, and by the combination of a Glans polarising prism and a Carl-Zeiss quarter-wave plate for the ultraviolet region. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE X.

 Conc. of $H_2T = 0.50M$. Conc. of uranyl = 0.50M. $p_n = 0.9$, Temp. = 28°.

Radiation.	Polarised light.	$I_{abs.}$ for all complexes.	$dx/dt \times 10^6$.		$r-H_2T$.
			$d-H_2T$.	$l-H_2T$.	
3130Å	<i>d</i> -circular	1040 ergs.	7.2	7.2	7.2
	<i>l</i> "	"	7.2	7.3	7.1
Whole visible	<i>d</i> - "	1120	14.6	14.6	14.7
	<i>l</i> "	"	14.5	14.5	14.8

There is no difference in the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-light, either visible or ultraviolet. For the same kind of polarised light, there is no difference in the velocity with complexes of *d*-, *l*- or racemic-acids.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The following mechanism can explain the main features of the photo-reduction of the uranyl nitrate-tartaric acid complex :

If k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 are the velocity constants for the processes (1), (2) and (3) respectively, we have for the velocity of the reaction the equation,

$$dx/dt = I_{\text{abs}} \times \frac{k_1 \times [\text{H}_2\text{T}]}{(k_2/k_3) + [\text{H}_2\text{T}]}$$

i.e., $I_{\text{abs}} \frac{dx}{dt}$ when plotted against $1/\text{conc. of H}_2\text{T}$, should give a straight line, as is actually the case. There is good agreement between the observed values of the velocity and those calculated from the above equation, wherein k_1 and k_2/k_3 have the values given in the above tables.

The author wishes to express his thanks to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for his kind interest in this work.

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Received June 6, 1942.